

Green and rapid approach for the synthesis of CuO/polyacrylonitrile and CuO/polymethyl methacrylate nanocomposites and their thermal stability

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CuO nanoparticles, CuO/polyacrylonitrile and CuO/polymethyl methacrylate nanocomposites were synthesized by microwave-assisted method. The CuO NPs were characterized by FT-IR and UV-Visible spectral studies. The size and morphology of CuO NPs have been determined by powder X-ray diffraction (P-XRD) and Transmission Electron Microscopic (TEM) studies. Nanocomposites have been characterised by IR, XPS and Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) studies. TEM images of CuO NPs revealed that most of the NPs were rod shape; however some of them have irregular shape with slight agglomeration with size range 3.21 nm to 24.09 nm. The thermal stability of nanocomposites has been determined by TG/DTA and indicated that CuO/PAN nanocomposite was more stable than CuO/PMMA.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, microwave-assisted synthesis, FTIR, P-XRD, Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM).

Introduction

In the last decades nanotechnology has become one of the most promising approaches for innovations that direct to fulfil the human needs. In recent years the nanocomposites have attracted a great attention of the researchers due to their diversified applications. It has been reported that addition of a very small amount of nanoparticles into the polymer matrix may alter many properties of polymer such as tensile modulus and strength, flexural modulus^{1,2}, thermal stability³⁻⁵, electrical conductivity⁶, flame retardation⁷ and other barrier resistance⁸. Nanocomposites have impacts on wide variety of industries including aerospace⁹, automotive¹⁰, microelectronics¹¹ industries. They are used as gas barrier, reinforcement agent and flame retardant¹², sensors^{13,14}, optical devices¹⁵⁻¹⁷, catalysts^{18,19}, electronic devices²⁰, non-linear optics²¹, food packaging²² materials. They also possess antimicrobial²³ and anticancer²⁴ activities. Unsaturated polyester (UPE) nanocomposites²⁵ can be employed as fibre reinforced products used in marine, transportation and construction industries. Core-shell Si/SiO nanocomposite²⁶ has been used to improve the electrochemical performance of anode materials for lithium ion batteries. Porous polymer nanocomposites can be used for the development of pollu-

tion²⁷ filter. A survey of literature revealed that only few attempts have been made on the synthesis of nanocomposites by adopting green chemistry approach like microwave assisted synthesis. In microwave heating the energy is directly transferred to the material through molecular interaction and, therefore, it has several beneficial effects, including reduced reaction time²⁸, rapid volumetric heating, selective heating. It also requires lower energy consumption, increased productivity²⁹ and an additional driving force for diffusion mechanism³⁰ compared to conventional thermal processing. In continuation of our research work³¹ on the green synthesis of nanocomposites in this paper we have reported microwave-assisted synthesis of CuO nanoparticles, two polymers polyacrylonitrile and polymethyl methacrylate, two nanocomposites, their characterization and thermal studies in a view to observe the morphology and thermal stability.

Results and discussion

Infrared spectral studies: IR spectra of synthesised copper nanoparticles exhibited the peaks at 675.87, 595.44, 500.63 and 487.59 cm⁻¹ due to Cu-O bond^{32,33}. The appearance of these bands indicated the formation of CuO nanoparticles. Polymer polyacrylonitrile (PAN) exhibited

bands at 2937.20, 2243.32, 1452.36, 1319.65 and 1073.06 cm^{-1} which may be attributed due to -C-H stretching vibrations³⁴, -C \equiv N stretching vibrations³³, -C-H bending vibrations³⁵ of CH₂, C-H bending vibrations of CH moiety and C-C stretching vibrations respectively. Polymethyl methacrylate polymer (PMMA) exhibited bands at 2997.93, 1733.80, 1193.70 and 1146.28 cm^{-1} which may be attributed due to C-H stretching vibrations³⁴ of methyl group, C=O stretching vibrations³⁵, O-CH₃ stretching vibrations³³ and -C-O-C stretching vibrations respectively. IR spectra of CuO/PAN nanocomposite exhibited the bands at 2935.79, 2243.32, 1453.27, 1384.62 and 1071.14 cm^{-1} which may be attributed due to C-H stretching vibrations³⁴, -C \equiv N stretching³³ vibrations, C-H bending vibrations of CH₂, C-H bending vibrations of CH moiety and C-C stretching vibrations respectively. In addition to above, some new bands at 685.65, 584.12, 477.82 cm^{-1} may be attributed due to Cu-O deformation vibrations. CuO/PMMA exhibited the peaks at 2952.37, 1733.67, 1193.30 and 1144.69 cm^{-1} due to C-H stretching vibrations³⁴ of methyl group, C=O stretching vibrations³⁵, O-CH₃ stretching vibrations³³ and C-O-C stretching vibrations respectively. The bands at 685.75, 590.79, 513.81 cm^{-1} have been attributed due to Cu-O deformation vibrations.

UV-Visible spectral studies: UV-Visible spectra of nanoparticles exhibited a strong band³⁶ at 300 nm and small bands at 292 nm, 287 nm which clearly indicated the formation of CuO nanoparticles.

P-XRD spectral studies: The structure and composition of synthesised copper oxide nanoparticles was determined by X-ray diffraction technique. The X-ray diffraction studies of synthesised copper oxide nanoparticles was carried out in the range of $2^\circ < 2\theta < 70^\circ$. The XRD spectra (Fig. 1) of synthesised nanoparticles showed that particles were crystalline in nature. Full width at half maximum has been used to find the size distribution of particles. It has been observed that the broader is the peak; broader is the size distribution of nanoparticles. Theoretical model suggested that the full width at half maximum increases with the increase in particle size³⁷. The crystalline domain size was calculated by the width of X-ray peaks, assuming that they are free from non-uniform strains, using Debye-Scherrer formula,

$$D = k \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$$

D is the average crystallite domain size perpendicular to the reflecting planes, λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) and θ is the diffraction angle.

On applying Debye-Scherrer formula on different peaks of XRD graph the sizes of the different nanoparticles were found 24.84, 10.35, 20.70, 8.87, 13.80, 18.24, 10.35, 10.30, 16.97 nm corresponding to 32.417, 35.681, 48.504, 53.414, 58.230, 61.433, 67.841, 72.273 and 74.866 2θ values. The average particle size of synthesised copper oxide nanoparticles has been found to be 14.93 nm.

X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopic studies: XPS spectrum of C 1s for PAN exhibited three peaks at 281.2, 284.1 and 287.3 eV which may be attributed to the C-H, C-C and

Fig. 1. XRD graph of CuO nanoparticles.

carbon attached with cyanide carbon³⁸ (CN) respectively. N 1s signal was appeared at 398.8 eV which may be assigned³⁹ to nitrogen atom of CN group.

The XPS spectra of CuO/PAN exhibited three peaks at 281.2, 284.1 and 287.6 eV which may be attributed to the C-H, C-C and carbon attached cyanide carbon (CN) respectively. Variation between the binding energy (BE) values of the PAN with respect to the CuO/PAN lies in the slight higher BE value of the last ionization peak, i.e. 0.3 eV, suggesting some chemical interactions between the -CN group and the Cu²⁺ ion of the CuO. N 1s signal for -CN group was appeared at 399.4 eV. The higher (0.6 eV) BE for nitrogen of -CN group confirms the interaction between the -CN group and the Cu²⁺ ions of the CuO⁴⁰. XPS spectrum of CuO/PAN nanocomposite also exhibited two more peaks of Cu 2p at 933.8 and 953.5 eV and these peaks are associated with the binding energy of 2p_{3/2} and Cu 2p_{1/2} respectively which conform the formation of nanocomposite. Surface elemental analysis results of CuO/PAN indicated the C, N, O and Cu contents were 27.16, 10.56, 12.07 and 47.94% respectively.

The XPS spectrum of C 1s for PMMA exhibited three peaks at 284.6, 286.2 and 288.6 eV due to the aliphatic and adventitious carbon (C-C), carbon bonded to one oxygen atom (C-O), and carbon of the -O-C=O group^{41,42} respectively. The O 1s signal of PMMA was composed by two peaks at 532.1 and 533.3 eV. These peaks were consistent with the oxygen of the C=O group and CH₃-O-C moiety respectively.

The XPS spectrum of C1s for CuO/PMMA nanocomposite exhibited three signals at 284.6, 286.3 and 289.2 eV due to the aliphatic and adventitious carbon (C-C), carbon bonded to one oxygen atom and carbon of the -O-C=O group respectively. The most evident variation between the binding energy (BE) values of the PMMA with respect to the CuO/PMMA lies in the slight higher BE value of the last ionization peak, i.e. 0.6 eV, suggesting some chemical interactions between the -C=O group and the Cu²⁺ ion of the CuO. The O 1s spectrum for the CuO/PMMA composite consists of two peaks at 532.4 and 533.3 eV, respectively. The higher (0.3 eV) BE for oxygen of -C=O group confirms the interaction between the -C=O group and the Cu²⁺ ions of the CuO⁴⁰. XPS spectrum of CuO/PMMA nanocomposite also exhibited two more peaks of Cu 2p at 933.8 and 953.5 eV and these peaks are associated with the binding energy of 2p_{3/2} and

Cu 2p_{1/2} respectively which conform the formation of nanocomposite. Surface elemental analysis results of CuO/PMMA showed that C, O and Cu contents were 33.41, 26.73 and 35.39% respectively.

Transmission electron microscopic studies: TEM images (Fig. 2) of synthesised nanoparticles indicated that the size of copper oxide nanoparticles exist in the range of 3.21 to 24.09 nm. The average size of copper oxide nanoparticles was found 14.57 nm. TEM images also indicated that the most of the nanoparticles were rod shape; however some of them have irregular shape with slight agglomeration.

Fig. 2. TEM images of copper oxide nanoparticles.

Scanning electron microscopic studies: SEM images (Fig. 3) of CuO/PAN composite indicated the formation of polymer shell around the CuO nanoparticles assisting the growth of core shell like structure⁴³ in which their surface is covered with polyacrylonitrile. SEM images (Fig. 4) of CuO/PMMA composite indicated that the CuO nanoparticles are highly dispersed⁴⁴ on the surface of polymer polymethyl methacrylate.

Thermogravimetric analysis: TG thermogram of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) indicated its degradation in 3 steps. In the first step degradation occurred between 114.40–184.10°C corresponding to weight loss 10.12%, second weight loss was found between 184.10–322.86°C corresponds to weight loss 37.16% and third weight loss was found between 322.86–400.50°C corresponds to weight loss 47.45%. DTA thermo-

Fig. 3. SEM images of CuO/polyacrylonitrile (CuO/PAN) nanocomposite.

Fig. 4. SEM images of CuO/polymethyl methacrylate (CuO/PMMA) nanocomposite.

gram indicated all these weight losses were accompanied by endothermic decomposition. TG thermogram of nanocomposite of CuO/PAN exhibited its degradation in 2 steps. In first step it was degraded at 110.92–224.64°C corresponding to weight loss 31.62%, second degradation occurred at 224.64–720.70°C corresponding to weight loss 56.30%. DTA curve results revealed both degradations take place by endothermic decomposition.

However, it has been observed that the thermal stability of nanocomposite CuO/PAN increased as compared to simple polymer polyacrylonitrile (PAN).

TG thermogram of polymethyl methacrylate exhibited degradation in 3 steps. First degradation occurred between 112.52–280.44°C corresponds to weight loss 9.07%, in second step it degraded between 280.44–370.37°C corresponds to weight loss 37.40% and third degradation occurred between 370.37–726.20°C corresponds to weight loss 39.52%. DTA curve of PMMA polymer indicated that these weight losses take place by endothermic decomposition. TG thermogram of nanocomposite of CuO/PMMA exhibited three steps degradation. It degraded first between 136.34–228.11°C corresponds to weight loss 16.97%. In second step it was degraded between 228.11–320.40°C corresponds to

weight loss 30.25%, third degradation occurred between 320.40–460.70°C corresponds to weight loss 41.12%. DTA graph indicated that these weight losses were take place with endothermic changes decomposition.

On comparing the TG/DTA thermograms of CuO/PMMA nanocomposite and simple PMMA polymer it has been observed that simple polymer PMMA has more thermal stability than nanocomposite CuO/PMMA.

Experimental

FT-IR spectroscopic studies were carried out in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} on Bruker spectrophotometer by using KBr pellets. UV-Visible spectroscopic study was carried out on Lab-India UV-Visible spectrophotometer UV 3000+ in DMSO at room temperature. The P-XRD analysis was carried out on XPERT-PRO X-ray diffractometer operated at a voltage of 45 kV and a current of 40 mA with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation in a θ - 2θ configuration. The TEM studies were carried out on model CM200, operated at an accelerating voltage of 20–200 kV with the resolution 2.4 Å. The Scanning Electron Microscopic studies has been carried out on JEOL Model JSM-6390LV operating at resolution of 3 nm (Acc V30 kV, WD 8 mm, SEI) to 8 nm (Acc V 1.0 kV, WD 6 mm, SEI) and magnification 5 x to 300,000 x (both in high and low vacuum modes), operating at a voltage of 1 pA to 1 mA. The TG/DTA analysis were carried out on model Perkin-Elmer, Diamond TG/DTA and TG measurement range 200 mg and TG sensitivity 0.2 mg. XPS analysis was carried out on PHI 5000 Versa prob II, FEI Inc.

All chemicals used in the experiments were analytical grade and used as received without further purification.

Synthesis of CuO nanoparticles: 3.98 g (0.4 M) copper (ii) acetate monohydrate was dissolved in 600 ml double distilled deionised water. To this solution, 2 ml glacial acetic acid was added. The solution was heated upto boiling in a microwave oven at an emitted power of 450 W for 3 min. The hot solution was stirred and 5 ml NaOH (6 M) solution was added drop by drop during stirring. The solution was further heated in microwave oven and 5 ml NaOH was added. This procedure was repeated until 35 ml NaOH was added. The mixture was again stirred for 2 h. After completion of reaction the mixture was cooled and centrifuged. The obtained precipitate was washed with deionised water for several times and followed by ethanol. The resulting product was dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Synthesis of CuO/polyacrylonitrile nanocomposite (CuO/PAN): 5 ml acrylonitrile and 10 mg benzoyl peroxide were mixed and 10 ml toluene was added to it. The contents were heated in a microwave oven at an emitted power of 140 W for 3 min by maintaining the temperature at 65–70°C. 0.05 mg of copper oxide nanoparticles suspended in water:HCl (3:1) was added in the viscous state of polyacrylonitrile. The viscous solution was further heated in the microwave oven for 2 min. The precipitation was done by using acidified CH₃OH (1 ml HCl + 5 ml CH₃OH) and then uniformly spread on a glass plate. A powdered material was obtained on drying in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. Similarly, polyacrylonitrile (PAN) was synthesized by omitting CuO nanoparticles.

Synthesis of CuO/polymethyl methacrylate nanocomposite (CuO/PMMA): 5 ml methyl methacrylate was mixed to the solution of 10 mg benzoyl peroxide and 10 ml toluene. The contents were subjected for microwave irradiation in an oven at an emitted power of 120 W for 4 min at an interval of 15 min. The temperature of reaction was maintained at 65–70°C. 0.05 mg of copper oxide nanoparticles was mixed in the sticky solution of polymethyl methacrylate. The solution was again heated in the microwave oven for 3 min. Finally, the precipitation was done by using acidified CH₃OH (1 ml HCl + 5 ml CH₃OH) and spread over a glass plate. On drying this plate at room temperature a thin film was obtained. Similarly, polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) was synthesized by omitting CuO nanoparticles.

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References

1. K. Kalaitzidou, H. Fukushima, H. Miyagawa and L. T. Drzal, *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, 2007, **47(11)**, 1796.
2. F. H. Chowdhury, M. V. Hosur and S. Jeelani, *Mat. Sci. Eng., A, Struct.*, 2006, **421(1-2)**, 298.
3. A. Niemczyk, K. Dziubek, B. Sacher-Majewska, K. Czaja, M. Dutkiewicz and B. Marciniec, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, 2016, **125**, 1287.
4. A. S. Pozdnyakov, A. I. Emel'yanov, N. P. Kuznetsova, T. G. Ermakova, T. V. Fadeeva, L. M. Sosedova and G. F. Prozorova, *Int. J. Nanomed.*, 2016, **11**, 1295.
5. G. Xu, S. Gao, X. Ji and X. Zhang, *Soft Nanoscience Letters*, 2014, **4**, 15.
6. P.-C. Ma, M.-Y. Liu, H. Zhang, S.-Q. Wang, R. Wang, K. Wang, Y.-K. Wong, B.-Z. Tang, S.-H. Hong, K.-W. Paik and J.-K. Kim, *ACS Appl. Mater. Inter.*, 2009, **1(5)**, 1090.
7. Y. Gao, J. Wu, Q. Wang, C. A. Wilkie and D. O' Hare, *J. Mater. Chem. (A)*, 2014, **2**, 10996.
8. H. Kwon, D. Kim and J. Seo, *Polym. Compos.*, 2016, **37(6)**, 1744.
9. A. A. Voevodin and J. S. Zabinski, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 2005, **65(5)**, 741.
10. J. M. Garces, D. J. Moll, J. Bicerano, R. Fibiger and D. G. McLeod, *Adv. Mater.*, 2000, **12(23)**, 1835.
11. H. Dong, A. Meininger, H. Jiang and C. P. Wong, *J. Electron. Mater.*, 2007, **36(5)**, 593.
12. M. Zammarano, M. Franceschi, S. Bellayer, J. W. Gilman and S. Meriani, *Polymer*, 2005, **46(22)**, 9314.
13. W. Chen, Z. Lu and C. M. Li, *Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **80(22)**, 8485.
14. R. Luoh and H. T. Hahn, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 2006, **66(14)**, 2436.
15. P. Zijlstra, J. W. M. Chon and M. Gu, *Opt. Express*, 2007, **15(19)**, 12151.
16. S. Qu, Y. Song, C. Du, Y. Wang, Y. Gao, S. Liu, Y. Li and D. Zhu, *Opt. Commun.*, 2001, **196(1-6)**, 317.
17. L. L. Beecroft and C. K. Ober, *Chem. Mater.*, 1997, **9(6)**, 1302.
18. S. Sunitha, A. N. Rao and J. Karthikeyan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **93**, 107.
19. E. Mosaddegh and A. Hassankhani, *Catal. Commun.*, 2015, **71**, 65.
20. W. E. Jones (Jr.), J. Chiguma, E. Johnson, A. Pachamuthu and D. Santos, *Materials*, 2010, **3(2)**, 1478.
21. K. Ozga, J. Michel, B. D. Nechporuk, J. Ebothe, I. V. Kityk, A. A. Albassam, A. M. El-Naggar and A. O. Fedorchuk, *Physica E: Low Dimens. Syst. Nanostruct.*, 2016, **81**, 281.
22. H. M. C. de Azeredo, *Food Res. Int.*, 2009, **42(9)**, 1240.
23. L. Balogh, D. R. Swanson, D. A. Tomalia, G. L. Hagnauer and A. T. McManus, *Nano Lett.*, 2001, **1(1)**, 18.
24. S. Rasouli, S. Davaran, F. Rasouli, M. Mahkam and R. Salehi, *Drug Deliv.*, 2014, **21(3)**, 155.
25. P. J. Schubel, A. J. Parsons, E. H. Lester, N. A. Warrior and C. D. Rudd, *Compos. Part A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2006, **37(10)**, 1747.
26. T. Zhang, J. Gao, H. P. Zhang, L. C. Yang, Y. P. Wu and H. Q. Wu, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2007, **9(5)**, 886.
27. H. Fischer, *Mater. Sci. Eng.: C*, 2003, **23(6-8)**, 763.

28. R. Shahid M. Gorlov, R. El-Sayed, M. S. Toprak, A. Sugunan, L. Kloo and M. Muhammed, *Mater. Lett.*, 2012, **89**, 316.
29. S. W. Chook, C. H. Chia, S. Zakaria, M. K. Ayob, K. L. Chee, N. M. Huang, H. M. Neoh, H. N. Lim, R. Jamal and R. M. F. R. A. Rahman, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.*, 2012, **7**, 541.
30. A. K. Rai, Ly. T. Anh, Chan-Jin Park and J. Kim, *Ceram. Int.*, 2013, **39(6)**, 6611.
31. D. Kumar, A. Jain and Neelam, *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.*, 2016, **8(10)**, 86.
32. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Application of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963.
33. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules: Advances in Infrared Group Frequencies", Vol. 2, Chapman and Hall, New York, 1980.
34. Y. R. Sharma, "Elementary Organic Spectroscopy", 12th ed., S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi, 2000.
35. R. M. Silverstein and F. X. Webster, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 6th ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1996.
36. R. Sankar, P. Manikandan, V. Malarvizhi, T. Fathima, K. S. Shivashangari and V. Ravikumar, *Spectrochim. Acta Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.*, 2014, **121**, 746.
37. R. Srivastava and D. Kumar, "Antibacterial Study of Metal Nanoparticles", 1st ed., Lap Lambert Academic Publishing, Germany, 2012.
38. S. N. M. Salleh, M. Z. Abdullah and A. A. Wahab, *MATEC Web Conf.*, 2014, **13**, 04014. doi: 10.1051/mateconf/2014 04014.
39. T. A. Bednaya and S. P. Konovalenko, *Journal of Physics: Conf. Series*, 2017, **857** 012002. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/857/1/012002.
40. P. Cui and A. J. Wang, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **20**, 343.
41. P. G. Mineo, D. A. Cristaldi, A. Motta, T. Gupta and A. Gulino, *RSC Adv.*, 2013, **3**, 1137.
42. K. Artyushkova and J. E. Fulghum, *J. Electr. Spectr. Rel. Phenom.*, 2001, **121**, 33.
43. C. Ramesh, M. Hariprasad, V. Ragunathan and N. Jayakumar, *Euro. J. Appl. Eng. Sci. Res.*, 2012, **1(4)**, 201.
44. S. B. Kondawar, S. P. Agrawal, S. H. Nimkar, H. J. Sharma and P. T. Patil, *Adv. Mat. Lett.*, 2012, **3(5)**, 393.